

SCIENTIFIC METHODOLOGICAL BASIS OF STUDYING THE COORDINATE ANGLE IN THE CONTEXT OF PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Abstract. *Having reviewed the school program for geometry in the basic school, it can be said that little attention is paid to the coordinate method. The section of the program "Objectives of studying the course coordinates in the primary school" considers: "when solving problems and proving theorems, geometric transformations and coordinates are used". This means that the program does not set the goal of studying the coordinate method as a method for solving geometric problems. The program states that "as a result of studying the geometry course, students should be able to use coordinates to solve simple problems".*

Keywords: *pedagogy, psychology, mathematics, teaching methods, coordinate method, learning, education, primary education.*

"Primary school is a fundamentally new stage in a child's life, systematic schooling begins, the sphere of interaction with the outside world expands, social status changes and the need for self-expression increases. There is a transition from the main play activity in preschool age to the formation of the leading educational activity in children of primary school age, in which the formation of the main mental and psychological characteristics of development in this period of the child's school life will take place"[1].

The main credit for the creation of the modern method of coordinates goes to the French philosopher, mathematician and naturalist René Descartes (1595-1650) - after whom rectangular coordinates are named. When coming to the theater, few people think about the origin of a simple thing: the numbering of seats by rows and seats. But once upon a time it was a big problem. The story has come down to us: Descartes, visiting Parisian theaters, was constantly surprised why there was such confusion and swearing when distributing the audience in the auditorium. It turns out that the rows and seats simply did not have numbers [18].

Then he proposed to introduce a numbering system in which each seat received a row number and a serial number from the edge. This system is still used today. An important place in the history of coordinates is occupied by the works of René Descartes: "Discourse on the Method" (1637) and "Geometry" (1637). In the first work, R. Descartes first scientifically described the rectangular coordinate system. That is why the rectangular coordinate system is also called the Cartesian coordinate system. In "Geometry", Descartes discovered and demonstrated the connection between algebra and geometry. He first introduced the concepts of variable quantity and function. This scientific work gave a huge impetus to the development of mathematics. In the Cartesian coordinate system, negative numbers received a real interpretation. The development of algebra and geometry for thousands of years proceeded independently of each other, there was a very weak connection between them. In the time of Descartes, these two branches had already reached a high level of development, but it was with the advent of analytical geometry that a new

direction in study appeared, establishing a close connection between geometry and algebra. Any point in space or a plane can be determined using numbers - its coordinates[15].

This means that any figure can be "encrypted" using numbers. The relationship between coordinates most often defines not one point, but a certain set (collection) of points. For example, if you mark all the points whose abscissa is equal to the ordinate, i.e. the points whose coordinates satisfy the equation, you will get a straight line - the bisectors of the first and third coordinate angles. (Fig. 1) Sometimes the concept of "set of points" is replaced by "geometrical location of points". For example, the geometrical location of points whose coordinates satisfy the relationship is the bisectors of the first and third coordinate angle. It was the discovery of the connection between algebra and geometry that gave impetus to a new direction in the development of mathematics. This knowledge began to develop mathematics as a single science, in which all its parts are inseparable from each other. One cannot fail to mention the French mathematician Pierre Fermat. His works made a great contribution to the development of the coordinate method, they were first published after his death. Fermat and Descartes studied the application of the coordinate method only on a plane, but in three-dimensional space, this method was first used by Leonard Euler in the 18th century. Coordinates make it possible to clearly depict the dependence of one value on another using a graph. In the modern world, this knowledge is widely used in various fields. That is why a large number of specialists in different fields have an idea of rectangular Cartesian coordinates on a plane [3].

In the school geometry course, there are various methods for solving problems and proving theorems. These include the synthetic method, the method of geometric transformations, the vector method and the method of coordinates, which in turn are interconnected. One or another method in school textbooks may take a predominant role, depending on the concept revealed by the authors [13].

Objectives:

- educational (development of cognitive universal learning activities):
development of students' skills and abilities in constructing points in a coordinate plane, determining the coordinates of a point located in a coordinate plane, correctly using the concepts of abscissa and ordinate.

- developmental (development of regulatory universal learning activities)
 - improvement of the level of development of students' speech through the use of mathematical terminology and mathematical language, the ability to process information and rank it according to the specified criteria; plan their activities depending on specific conditions; control and evaluation of the process and results of activities, development of skills of independent work and work in pairs, self-control and mutual control, development of interest in the subject through entertaining and creative tasks.

- educational (development of communicative and personal universal learning activities):
ability to listen and enter into dialogue, participate in a collective discussion of problems, cultivate responsibility and accuracy, the ability to overcome difficulties by solving difficult but interesting problems, cultivate an exemplary attitude to study, interest in the subject.

Sel: 1) to develop children's translatable ideas and improve their orientation to the topic.

2) to expand the mathematical scope of the student.

I. Organizational moment.

- Tell me what you learn from the lesson? What do you want from each other?

You learn more, but you can call it notes, because you know and understand a lot. Today I have to answer many questions, both to help experts and to learn something new, because a person lives while he studies and learns something new.

II. Working on a number

Using the digits of the date, make up the largest four-digit number.

III. Mental arithmetics

- increase this number by 1 thousand;
- decrease the number by 2 times;
- increase by 2 times;
- increase by 2 tens 1 unit;
- decrease by 3 thousands;
- find the sum of all the digits;
- find the difference of all the digits;
- increase the number by 3 hundreds 3 tens;
- decrease by 9 units

Write the numbers in ascending order. And read the type of the next task.

IV. Knowledge Update

Crossword

- 1) A part of a straight line that has a beginning but no end. (Ray).
- 2) A geometric figure that has no angles. (Circle).
- 3) The smallest geometric figure. (Point).
- 4) A geometric figure that has the shape of an elongated circle. (Oval).

The topic of our lesson is hidden vertically. Find it. (Angle).

- What is an angle?
- What geometric figures does an angle consist of?
- What is a ray?
- Are these geometric figures rays? Prove it.
- Which ray is different from the others?
- What is it called?

Read the name of the beam?

D. Ox

U. What letter marks the beginning of the beam?

D. 0

How do the numerical beams (1,2) differ from each other?

D. Unit segments. For beam 1, the unit segment is equal to one cell, for beam 2, the unit segment is equal to two cells.

U. Find point A with coordinate 5 on beam 1, point B with coordinate 3 on beam 2 and mark them. (Students come to the board and complete the tasks).

As a result, these beams look like this:

We have remembered what a coordinate ray "looks like". Think about how a coordinate angle "looks" on a drawing?

D. These are two number rays emanating from one point in the form of an angle.

U. Correct.

V. Message about the topic and objectives of the lesson:

Formulate the topic and tasks that need to be solved in the lesson.

- Find out how to construct a coordinate angle;
- Find out what the rays and points of a coordinate ray are called;
- Where a coordinate angle can be useful;

VI. Working on new material.

Open your textbook .

The Wolf and the Hare bought tickets for a football match. In which row and in what place will each sit?

On one ray we will mark the place, on the other - the row.

Name in which row and in what place are the Boa Constrictor, Giraffe, Hedgehog sitting?

Let's agree, guys, that when answering these questions, you will first name the place of the spectator, and then the row in which he sits.

Points are marked on the coordinate angle.

- What did we do?
- We named the place of the animals or their COORDINATES.

How many values does the coordinate have?

- How to construct a coordinate angle?

CONCLUSION:

1. We choose a point - the origin of the coordinates.

2. From it we draw 2 rays at a right angle.

Find the name of these rays in the textbook

3. We put off a unit segment on the rays

4. We mark a point according to the given coordinates. (How many values does the coordinate have?)

- Where in life can the coordinate angle be used?

VII. Reinforcing primary knowledge.

Name the pairs of numbers corresponding to the vertices of each figure.

Work in pairs

What word is encrypted in the picture if the letters are read in the order in which the pairs of numbers follow?

(3,6); (5,0); (1,4); (6,5); (0,2); (4,3)

Independent work

On the coordinate beam. Mark the coordinates:

A1 (3,2); A2 (2,3); A3 (4,3); A4 (4,7); A5 (6,4); A6 (7,3); A7 (6,2).

Connect the dots in the following order A1, A2, A3, A4, A5, A3, A6, A7, A1.

What picture did you get?

VIII. Lesson Summary. Reflection. "Today I learned."

At the beginning of the lesson we set tasks. Did we complete them? Let's check.

Having reviewed the school program for geometry in the basic school, it can be said that little attention is paid to the coordinate method. The section of the program "Objectives of studying the course coordinates in the primary school" considers: "when solving problems and proving theorems ... geometric transformations and coordinates are used". This means that the program does not set the goal of studying the coordinate method as a method for solving geometric problems. The program states that "as a result of studying the geometry course, students should be able to use coordinates to solve simple problems".

According to the concept of M. Dzhumaev, "the age of 6-12 years is considered as a period of transferring systematic knowledge and skills to the child, ensuring introduction to working life and aimed at developing diligence". The most important new formations arise in all areas of mental development: intellect, personality, and social relations are transformed. The leading role of educational activity in this process does not exclude the fact that the younger schoolchild is actively involved in other types of activity, during which the child's new achievements are improved and consolidated[12].

The solution of problems by the coordinate method is carried out according to an algorithm, which in turn simplifies the search and the solution of the problem itself. This method transfers an important feature of algebra to geometry - the uniformity of methods for solving a particular problem. Unlike arithmetic and elementary geometry, in algebra and analytical geometry the solution of problems is given according to a plan common to all problems, practically suitable for any problem. The use of the coordinate method for solving geometric problems eliminates the need for a visual representation of complex spatial images[16].

The essence of the coordinate method as a method for solving problems is that, by defining figures with equations and expressing various geometric relationships in coordinates, we can solve a geometric problem by means of algebra. The coordinate method is a universal method. It ensures

a close connection between algebra and geometry, which, when combined, give "rich fruits" that they could not give if they remained separate[14].

Quite simple to use, the coordinate method is a necessary component of solving problems at various levels. Using this method allows students to significantly simplify and shorten the process of solving problems, which helps them in further study, both in the school mathematics course and in studying mathematics in higher educational institutions.

Thus:

- 1) several current school textbooks on the topic "Coordinate Method" were analyzed;
- 2) the coordinate method itself, types and stages of solving problems using the coordinate method were described;
- 3) the main skills necessary for mastering this method were identified and a number of tasks that form them were given.
- 4) a lesson plan with a process map was developed

Also, a hypothesis was put forward that studying the coordinate method in the school geometry course is necessary. It will be more effective if in grades 5-6 propaedeutic work was carried out to form basic skills and abilities, in the systemic course of planimetry, students are introduced to the structure of this method, and a well-thought-out system of tasks is used to form individual components of the method[9].

In the process of studying and acquiring new knowledge, skills and abilities about geometric representations, the main role is played by observations and practical activities of students. The formation of ideas goes from the object imagined by the child in the head - to the form of a geometric figure as its image and, accordingly, vice versa, from a certain figure-image - to a real object. Studying geometry in primary school makes it possible to introduce children to a completely different side of the mathematical way of knowing the world around them compared to the arithmetic side, and a large number of geometric forms and methods of knowing them makes it possible to show them the aesthetic side of mathematics.

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